

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THE ECONOMIC AND STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE EFFICIENCY OF INVESTMENT UTILIZATION IN THE REGIONAL INDUSTRIAL SECTOR

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Abstract. This article discusses the specific features of the economic and statistical analysis of the efficiency of investment use in the regional industrial sector. Also, conclusions are presented on the economic and statistical analysis of the efficiency of investment use in the regional industrial sector.

Key words. Region, industry, industrial sector, investment, efficiency, analysis, economic and statistical analysis.

Investments are considered a key factor in the economic development and sustainable growth of countries and regions. They contribute to expanding production capacity, creating new jobs, improving infrastructure, and increasing the level of industrialization. In this regard, a number of studies have examined issues related to industrial efficiency. In particular, the efficiency of industrial production depends on sectoral resources and their ability to transform into the necessary outcomes to achieve specific objectives within the production process [1]. Other studies have explored approaches to the economic and statistical analysis of the efficiency of investment utilization in the regional industrial sector. According to these studies, the efficiency of a regional economy is based on the interconnection and functioning of product, labor, investment, capital, and innovation markets; the creation and distribution chain of value added; economic potential; property institutions; and external opportunities [2]. According to additional research, the efficiency of investment utilization in industry and other sectors across regions is aimed at identifying regional disparities. In particular, these studies address the effective use of investments in reducing regional disparities in the socio-economic development of Uzbekistan, improving the territorial structure of investments in fixed capital, as well as foreign investments and attracted loans, and analyzing existing problems and their solutions in this sphere [3].

In the Khorezm region and its territories, the volume of investments demonstrated positive changes during 2010-2024. Accordingly, the growth rate of gross regional product also showed high performance indicators. However, increasing the volume of investments alone is not sufficient to raise the level of industrialization, economic activity, and the scale of innovation in the region and

its territories. This is because the process of utilizing investments is multi-factorial and structurally complex. First and foremost, attention should be paid to the efficiency of investment utilization. This requires assessing the use of capital in the Khorezm region and its territories, its efficiency, and its optimal and rational allocation. Before addressing these issues, we analyze the volume of investments and their changing trends. The total volume of investments directed to the Khorezm region increased significantly from 310.6 billion UZS in 2010 to 12,380.3 billion UZS in 2024, reflecting nearly a 40-fold increase over the study period. Particularly rapid growth was observed between 2017 and 2021, when investments increased from 2.2 trillion UZS in 2017 to 8.3 trillion UZS in 2021. This trend can be explained by the expansion of infrastructure projects, industrial clusters, and tourism infrastructure investments in the region.

Nevertheless, the scale of investments differs across the region's territories. For example, investments directed to Urgench city increased from 54.4 billion UZS in 2010 to 2,808.9 billion UZS in 2024, indicating intensified industrial and service activities. Positive changes were also observed in Khiva city, largely due to increased investments in tourism and cultural heritage infrastructure. In Bagat, Gurlan, Khanka, Kushkupir, and Urgench districts, investment volumes grew steadily, mainly in high value-added industrial and agricultural activities. The highest growth rates were recorded in Yangiarik and Yangibazar districts, where investments were primarily directed toward agricultural processing and water management facilities. Thus, differences in investment levels among territories are explained by variations in economic potential, logistics capacity, workforce qualifications, and availability of natural resources.

It should be emphasized that merely increasing investment volumes is insufficient to ensure economic stability. The creation of new jobs, growth in production volume and quality, and improvements in living standards are of crucial importance. According to the analysis, the statistical assessment of capital efficiency in the Khorezm region generally demonstrated growth. Tuprakkal'a, Urgench and Gurlan districts were leading in this regard. However, regional imbalances have persisted and even intensified over time. In many districts, the comparative indicator of capital efficiency differs by 5-6 times. In Tuprakkal'a it reached 13 units, whereas in Khiva city it remained at the lowest level of 1.0-1.3 units. While the gap between the highest and lowest indicators was 1.6 times at the beginning of the study period, by 2024 it had increased to 13.2 times, reflecting significant disproportionality.

The capital return indicator in the industrial sector characterizes the production capacity of a territory, its technological development level, and the efficiency of investment resource utilization. It demonstrates the extent to which investments in industrial sectors generate economic returns. The industry of the Khorezm region includes food processing, construction materials, light industry, and mechanical engineering, and capital return allows for assessing investment efficiency in these sectors. Between 2010 and 2024, the average capital return in the region's industrial sector declined from 2.0 units to 1.6 units, though it fluctuated throughout the period. It ranged between 1.7-2.1 units during 2010-2013, 1.3-1.7 during 2014-2016, and 1.9-2.1 during 2017-2019. From 2020 onward, capital return declined significantly, reaching 1.6 units in 2021-2024. This is related to the capital-intensive nature of industrial projects and the long payback periods of investments.

Territorial analysis shows specific features. Urgench city, as an industrial center, had a leading capital return of 4.7 units in 2010, but this decreased to 1.1 units by 2024. This decline can be explained by the fact that investments increased by 128.3 percent while industrial production grew by 110.6 percent, leading to a higher capital base relative to output. In Gurlan, Kushkupir, Yangiariq and Yangibazar districts, capital return remained low due to the predominance of small industrial enterprises focused on processing agricultural raw materials into food and textile products. The regional average capital return of 1.6 units indicates low production efficiency, reflecting the dominance of energy-intensive and low-technology industries. The analysis shows that although investment volumes in the industrial sector of the Khorezm region have increased annually, their economic efficiency has remained low and capital return has shown a declining trend. Therefore, it is necessary to expand enterprises engaged in deep processing of agricultural products, promote export-oriented production, and broaden state-funded projects through public-private partnerships. The statistical analysis of capital return in the Khorezm region's industrial sector enables assessment of sectoral potential growth, investment efficiency, and intersectoral coordination. Although industrial activity increased rapidly during the study period, the efficiency of investment utilization did not progress uniformly across territories.

Data indicate that between 2010 and 2024, the comparative capital return indicator in the regional industrial sector increased from an average of 2.0 units to 6.1 units relative to the lowest-performing territory. Between 2010-2014, the indicator remained around 2.0 units, reflecting the formation stage of the

industrial base. During 2015-2018 it ranged from 2.4-3.0 units, and in 2019-2021 it increased to 4.0-8.6 units. Particularly during 2020-2024, the statistical assessment of capital return rose sharply, associated with the establishment of new industrial zones, expansion of processing industries, and industrial reforms implemented under state programs. Tuprakkal'a, Hazarasp, Urgench emerged as leading territories in industrial efficiency due to large enterprises and new production capacities. In other territories, a significant portion of industrial capital remains concentrated in processing and construction materials industries, while the share of high-tech investments remains low.

In conclusion, from 2010 to 2024 the Khorezm region experienced significant growth in investment and capital activity, with investment volumes increasing nearly 40 times. However, despite increased investment volumes, economic efficiency and capital return declined to some extent. In other words, while investments increased, their profitability coefficient remained relatively low. This situation necessitates a qualitative revision of investment policy, focusing not only on increasing the volume of investments but also on improving their efficiency, capital return, profitability, and sustainability.

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